

12th International Manikin and Modelling Meeting
29-31 August 2018, St. Gallen, Switzerland

Modelling and validation of comfort temperature for bedding system

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1404550

Yuping Liu¹, Yehu Lu^{1,2*}

¹College of Textile and Clothing Engineering, Soochow University, Suzhou, China

²National Engineering Laboratory for Modern Silk, Suzhou, China

Corresponding author: yhlu@suda.edu.cn

Introduction

The total thermal insulation of bedding system includes the quilt, mattress, pillow, sleepwear and air layer surrounding the human body, which is one of the key factors affecting the thermal comfort in sleeping environments. Recent studies showed that good quality of sleep can be maintained in a wide range of low temperatures by changing the total thermal insulation of the bedding system [1,2]. However, there is no guideline for selecting proper quilt for a specific environment, comparing with sleeping bags as summarized by Huang [3]. Consumers can only buy a bedding system via the weight and filling content based on their experience. Improper use of bedding system cannot guarantee a comfortable sleeping.

In this study, a thermal comfort model was developed to predict the minimum ambient temperature for a comfortable restful sleep based on the general energy balance equation. The relationship between the total thermal insulation of bedding system and ambient temperature was established. Human trial tests were further performed to validate the model. The purpose of this study was to develop a prediction model for guiding the selection of bedding system in a specific sleeping environment, and provide theoretical basis for the design of bedding system.

Methods

Model development Based on heat balance equation of human body, a thermal comfort model was developed to predict required thermal insulation of bedding system in a specific ambient temperature to keep a sleeper comfort during whole night. The metabolic rate was 46.5 W/m^2 (0.8 met) and mean skin temperature of $32 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ was used as the lower limit to keep a sleeper comfort. Other parameters were referenced in EN 13537.

Thermal insulation test The total thermal insulation (R_c) of bedding system was measured using 34-zone thermal manikin 'Newton' according to ISO 15831(2004) and calculated using parallel method. The quilts (Q1~Q6) are $150\text{cm}\times 200\text{cm}$, and the filling weights are 50, 100, 150, 200, 250 and 300g/m^2 respectively. The mattress, pillow and sleepwear remained unchanged. Taking these thermal insulation values into the model, the corresponding ambient temperature will be obtained.

Model validation Six male subjects (BMI: $21.7\pm 0.9 \text{ kg/m}^2$) and six female subjects (BMI: $20.2\pm 1.0 \text{ kg/m}^2$) were involved to validate the model in a climate chamber. The experiment lasted for 8 hours. The local skin temperatures and heart rate were continuously monitored throughout the sleep experiment. The mean skin temperature (T_{sk}) was calculated using the Gagge and Nishi equation (8-point). The metabolic rate during sleeping was also measured. The subjective thermal sensation and comfort sensation were recorded at the beginning, 20 min and the end of the test.

Temperature setting The temperature in the climate chamber was firstly set at the predicted ambient temperature. According to the test results, the chamber temperature was adjusted to make the subjects feel not cold or hot, and the subjects did not wake up or sweat during the whole sleep. If the subjects feel warm/cold, the ambient temperature can reduce/increase $1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ until they reach the comfort state. The average temperature was considered as the comfort temperature when the subjects feel warm and cool in two environmental conditions.

Results and discussion

The total thermal insulation was shown in Table 1. It is in the range of 2.52-4.01 clo. Generally, the total thermal insulation of bedding system increases with the filling weight.

Table 1. Total thermal insulation of bedding system and predicted temperature

	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6
Total thermal insulation (clo)	2.52	3.31	3.51	3.70	3.87	4.01
Predicted comfort temperature(°C)	17.9	13.3	12.1	11.0	10.0	9.2

Based on the general energy balance equation, a theoretical prediction model for keeping a sleeper comfort is established. The relationship between the ambient temperature (t_a) and the total thermal insulation of bedding system (R_c) is as follows

$$t_a = -5.8529R_c + 32.66 \quad (1)$$

The comfort temperature was predicted and shown in Table 1. The usage range of six quilts covers from summer to winter. Figure 1 shows the validation of this model. For the same bedding system, the comfort temperature for male subjects is lower than that for female subjects during sleep. The regressed model is $t_a = -5.8597R_c + 32.022$ ($R^2=0.975$). The overall difference between the actual ambient temperature and the predicted temperature is -0.8 – 0.3 °C. The minor difference might be caused by empirical parameters used in the model and the actual comfort temperature determination method. The prediction accuracy is acceptable.

Figure 1. The validation of the comfort model

Conclusions

A thermal comfort model for predicting comfort temperature of bedding system was developed in this study. The predicted comfort temperature is negatively correlated with the total thermal insulation of bedding system. It is found that the measured ambient temperature is pretty close to the predicted temperature, which demonstrates the feasibility of the theoretical model.

References

1. Lin, Z., & Deng, S. (2008). A study on the thermal comfort in sleeping environments in the subtropics—developing a thermal comfort model for sleeping environments. *Building & Environment*, 43(1), 70-81.
2. Lin, Z., & Deng, S. (2008). A study on the thermal comfort in sleeping environments in the subtropics—measuring the total insulation values for the bedding systems commonly used in the subtropics. *Building & Environment*, 43(5), 905-916.
3. Huang, J. (2008). Prediction of air temperature for thermal comfort of people using sleeping bags: a review. *International Journal of Biometeorology*, 52(8), 717-723.